

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF LEACH PROTOCOL IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS USING AN EMPIRICAL PATH LOSS MODEL FOR FARM MICROCLIMATE MONITORING

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Abstract: *Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are increasingly deployed in precision agriculture to enable real-time monitoring of soil moisture, temperature, and humidity. However, their effectiveness is constrained by limited node energy and the propagation losses introduced by vegetation-rich environments. This study investigates the performance of the Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (LEACH) protocol in ZigBee-based WSNs using an empirical path loss model derived from cassava farm measurements, in contrast to conventional free-space and two-ray theoretical assumptions. The empirical model captures attenuation and multipath effects induced by dense crop canopies, thereby providing a more realistic basis for protocol evaluation. Simulations were conducted in Matrix Laboratory (MATLAB) under varying cluster head (CH) percentages, node densities, and packet sizes, with Average Energy Consumption and Network Lifetime employed as the principal performance metrics. Results demonstrate that a CH ratio of 10%, a node density of 60, and a packet size of 400 bits collectively minimized energy dissipation while maintaining adequate coverage and extended network lifetime. Moreover, the Empirical Energy Model (EEM) consistently predicted substantially higher energy consumption than the Theoretical Energy Model (TEM), which underestimated dissipation by neglecting vegetation-induced effects. The findings underscore the necessity of incorporating empirical propagation models for accurate evaluation of WSNs in agricultural deployments and provide a robust foundation for the design of sustainable microclimate monitoring systems.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Precision agriculture has become a cornerstone of modern farming, providing data-driven solutions to the challenges of food security, environmental sustainability, and resource optimization (Thangamani *et al.*, 2025). At the core of this practice is microclimate monitoring, which supplies continuous measurements of soil moisture, temperature, and humidity variables essential for irrigation scheduling, yield forecasting, and adaptive responses to environmental stress. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are increasingly adopted in agricultural monitoring because they provide scalable, cost-effective infrastructure for distributed sensing of soil moisture, temperature, and humidity (Abdollahi *et al.*, 2021). In precision agriculture applications, WSNs support data-driven irrigation, resource optimization, and sustainability goals (Jawad *et al.*, 2017). When deployed in precision agriculture, WSNs enhance productivity, reduce resource wastage, and support sustainable farming practices.

Among available communication standards, ZigBee has gained prominence due to its low energy consumption, robustness in short-range transmission, and ability to form mesh topologies that extend coverage in remote agricultural fields (Mowla *et al.*, 2023).

Despite these advantages, energy efficiency remains a fundamental challenge since most sensor nodes depend on limited battery energy and communication costs dominate overall consumption. Clustering protocols such as the Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (LEACH) have been widely studied to address this issue. LEACH prolongs network lifetime by designating cluster heads (CHs) that aggregate and transmit data to a sink node, thereby reducing redundant transmissions and balancing energy expenditure across the network (Abose *et al.*, 2024). A generic structure of a cluster-based Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is illustrated in Figure 1, where nodes are organized into clusters with designated CHs responsible for communication with the base station.

Figure 1: A cluster-based Wireless Sensor Network

Nevertheless, the protocol is limited by its probabilistic CH selection mechanism, uneven load distribution, and susceptibility to propagation conditions in real agricultural environments. More critically, most previous evaluations of LEACH rely on simplified propagation models such as free space or two-ray ground assumptions, which neglect the vegetation-induced attenuation that characterizes realistic farm settings. These oversimplifications often result in inflated estimates of network performance and restrict the applicability of simulation outcomes to practical deployments.

Cassava farms, for instance, present particularly challenging propagation environments due to their dense canopy cover, closely spaced stems, and high foliage moisture content, all of which

increase path loss and degrade communication reliability. Empirical studies have demonstrated that vegetation-specific environments impose significant deviations from theoretical models (Anastassiou *et al.*, 2014; Ateya *et al.*, 2017), yet few investigations have integrated such empirical path loss characteristics into WSN protocol evaluation. This study addresses this gap by analysing the performance of the LEACH protocol in ZigBee-based WSNs under an empirical path loss model derived from cassava farm measurements. The contributions are threefold: first, empirical propagation effects are incorporated into WSN simulations; second, the impact of these effects on energy consumption, lifetime, and node survivability is systematically evaluated; and third, optimal protocol configurations are identified for sustainable

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deployment of microclimate monitoring systems in precision agriculture.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

WSNs have gained prominence in precision agriculture as cost-effective solutions for monitoring soil and crop microclimates. They enable continuous measurements of temperature, humidity, and soil moisture, which support data-driven decision making for irrigation, fertilization, and disease prevention. Hudda and Haribabu (2025) reviewed WSN applications in smart farming and emphasized that energy consumption remains the principal limitation of large-scale deployments. ZigBee has been widely adopted in precision agriculture because of its low power requirements, short-range robustness, and ability to form mesh networks. Li *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that ZigBee radios consume substantially less power than Wi-Fi modules under comparable operating conditions, making them more suitable for energy-constrained deployments. Vougioukas *et al.* (2013) further reported that while ZigBee provides stable performance in greenhouse and orchard monitoring, its signals are significantly affected by foliage-induced attenuation and multipath effects. These studies highlighted both the suitability of ZigBee for agricultural monitoring and the challenges posed by vegetation-rich environments.

In order to address energy constraints, clustering protocols such as LEACH have been

extensively studied. LEACH reduces redundant transmissions by designating rotating CHs to aggregate and forward data, thereby balancing node energy consumption. Abu Salem and Shudifat (2019) demonstrated that an enhanced version of LEACH significantly improves network lifetime by optimizing cluster formation, while Al-Zubaidi *et al.* (2018) proposed stability improvements to the protocol to extend its applicability in dense deployments. Dwivedi and Sharma (2021) further introduced Energy Enhanced Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (EE-LEACH), which incorporates fuzzy logic to achieve more efficient CH selection and energy distribution. More recently, Verma (2023) highlighted parameter optimization in LEACH as a means of improving routing efficiency and prolonging network lifetime. These studies collectively underscored the continuous evolution of LEACH variants toward more energy-efficient and robust WSN performance. Despite these innovations, most evaluations assume simplified propagation models such as free space or two-ray ground, which overlook environmental factors that critically influence communication reliability. As a result, reported gains often lack practical validity when applied to real farm conditions.

Vegetation-induced attenuation has been highlighted in several empirical studies. Aldosary and Kostanic (2017) showed that tree-obstructed propagation environments significantly increase path loss and degrade packet delivery in WSNs, while Alsayyari and

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Aldosary (2019) confirmed similar deviations from theoretical predictions in long-grass environments. Anastassiou *et al.* (2014) and Ateya *et al.* (2017) also reported substantial foliage-related losses, reinforcing the inadequacy of canonical propagation models for agricultural settings. More recent investigations have extended this perspective. For instance, Cama-Pinto *et al.* (2023) examined greenhouse conditions, Phaiboon and Phokharatkul (2024) analysed path loss in ruby mango plantation environments, and Barrios-Ulloa *et al.* (2023) applied machine learning to model path loss in cassava fields. Despite these advances, very few studies have integrated empirical propagation models into the performance evaluation of clustering protocols such as LEACH. This gap is particularly critical in crops like cassava, where dense canopy cover, stem spacing, and high foliage moisture create complex propagation conditions. The present study addresses this gap by evaluating LEACH under realistic empirical models, thereby providing a more accurate foundation for sustainable WSN-based microclimate monitoring.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The general form of the two-slope log-distance model is expressed in Equation (1):

$$PL(d_i) = \begin{cases} PL(d_b) + 10n_1 \log\left(\frac{d_i}{d_b}\right) & d_i \leq d_b \\ PL(d_{b+1}) + 10n_2 \log\left(\frac{d_i}{d_{b+1}}\right) & d_i > d_b \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

3.1 Development of Empirical Radio Energy Model

The path loss model employed in this work was derived from an earlier investigation by Iyaomolere *et al.* (2024), where the two-slope log-distance model was applied to characterize radio wave propagation of ZigBee-based WSNs in a cassava farm environment. The investigation was conducted within the context of farm microclimate monitoring, with sensor nodes deployed to measure environmental variables such as temperature, humidity, and soil moisture. The model was formulated using received signal strength indicator (RSSI) measurements and least-squares regression analysis, and it was shown to effectively capture the attenuation effects caused by dense canopy cover, stem spacing, and high foliage moisture content. In the present study, this empirically derived model was adopted and integrated into the radio energy framework in order to ensure that the performance evaluation of the LEACH protocol reflects realistic propagation conditions in vegetation-rich farm environments.

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where $PL(d_b)$ is the path loss at the reference distance of 1 m, n_1 and n_2 denote the path loss exponents before and after the breakpoint, and d_b

is the breakpoint distance at which the line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) propagation curves intersect.

The relationship between path loss, transmit power, and received power is defined in Equation (2):

$$PL[dB] = P_t[dBm] - P_r[dBm] + G_t[dB] + G_r[dB] \tag{2}$$

where P_t is the transmit power, P_r is the received power, G_t and G_r are the gain of the transmitter and receiver antennas respectively. In this study, the XBee-S2C modules were configured with a transmit power of 8 dBm, while the antenna

gains were set to 2 dBi at both the transmitting and receiving ends.

The empirical path loss model obtained in the earlier cassava farm study is presented in Equation (3) (Iyaomolere *et al.*, 2024):

$$PL(d) = \begin{cases} 43.33 + 25.52 \log(d) & d \leq d_b \\ 22.10 + 42.52 \log(d) & d > d_b \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Figure 2: A typical radio energy model for WSN simulations (Aldosary and Kostanic, 2017)

This model is directly incorporated into the radio energy model, illustrated conceptually in Figure 2, to provide realistic estimates of the energy required for wireless transmissions in farm environments.

Accordingly, the transmission energy for an L-bit message over a distance, d is given in Equation (4):

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$$E_{TX}(L, d) = \begin{cases} E_{elec} + E_{amp}(n_1) \times L \times d^{2.55} & d \leq d_b \\ E_{elec} + E_{amp}(n_2) \times L \times d^{4.25} & d > d_b \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where E_{TX} represents the transmission energy, E_{amp} is the radio amplifier energy coefficients, and E_{elec} is the energy consumed by the electronics for data communication and expressed in Equation (5);

$$E_{elec} = \frac{I_{TX} \times V_s \times L}{R_B} \quad (5)$$

Where R_B is the bit rate of the radio, I_{TX} are the current drawn during data transmission, V_s is the voltage supplied and L is the message length.

$$E_{amp}(n_1, n_2) = \begin{cases} \frac{P_{r.th} \times 10^{4.333}}{R_B \times G_t \times G_r} & d \leq d_b \\ \frac{P_{r.th} \times 10^{2.210}}{R_B \times G_t \times G_r} & d > d_b \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where $P_{r.th}$ is the receiver sensitivity threshold. Finally, the energy required to receive an L-bit message is given in Equation (7):

$$E_{RX} = \frac{I_{TX} \times V_s \times L}{R_B} \quad (7)$$

Where E_{TX} represents the reception energy and I_{RX} are the current drawn during data reception. The current values used in Equations (5) and (7) were experimentally determined by measuring the current drawn by an XBee S2C module during data communication using a digital Multimeter. Together, Equations (4) – (7) constitute the empirical radio energy model adopted in this work. By embedding the cassava-farm-specific propagation model into the energy framework, the study ensures that the simulation-based analysis of the LEACH protocol accounts for the realistic energy dissipation patterns experienced in agricultural microclimate monitoring deployments.

The amplifier energy coefficients are expressed in Equation (6) by combining Equations (2) and (3):

3.2 LEACH Protocol

The LEACH protocol was adopted in this study as the clustering and data aggregation mechanism for the wireless sensor network. LEACH is a hierarchical routing protocol specifically designed to minimize energy consumption in WSNs through randomized rotation of CHs, localized coordination, and in-network data aggregation (Kandris *et al.*, 2023). The operation of LEACH is divided into two primary phases: the set-up phase and the steady-state phase. In the set-up phase, CHs are selected probabilistically, and the network is organized into clusters. Each non-CH node joins the CH with the strongest received signal strength, thereby optimizing intra-cluster communication

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distance. In the steady-state phase, data transmission is performed using Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) schedules, where member nodes send their sensed data to the CH. The CH aggregates the received data before forwarding it to the Base Station (BS), thereby

reducing redundant transmissions and conserving energy (Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2023). The process of cluster formation and data transmission in LEACH is depicted in the flowchart shown in Figure 3, while the detailed algorithmic steps are summarized in the pseudocode provided in Table 1.

Figure 3: Flowchart of LEACH Protocol (Tadros *et al.*, 2023)

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Table 1: Pseudocode of the LEACH Protocol

Algorithm 1: LEACH Protocol
Input: WSN with N sensor nodes, desired CH probability p , round counter r Output: Aggregated data delivered to Base Station (BS) Begin: 1 : Initialize network: set node energy, status \leftarrow member 2 : repeat // One round 3 : Cluster Head Selection 4 : $G \leftarrow \{ \text{nodes not CH in last } \lfloor 1/p \rfloor \text{ rounds} \}$ 5 : For each node $i \in G$ do 6 : Compute threshold $T(i) = p / (1 - p \times (r \bmod \lfloor 1/p \rfloor))$ 7 : If $\text{random}(0,1) < T(i)$ then assign node i as CH 8 : End For 9 : If no CH elected, force highest-energy node as CH 10 : Cluster Formation 11 : Each non-CH node joins nearest CH (based on RSSI/distance) 12 : CHs create and broadcast TDMA schedule to members 13 : Data Transmission & Energy Update 14 : For each member node m do 15 : Sense data, send to CH in allocated slot 16 : Update energy for Tx and Rx 17 : End For 18 : Each CH aggregates received data, transmits to BS 19 : Update energy for CH transmission 20 : Mark nodes with $E \leq 0$ as dead 21 : $r \leftarrow r + 1$ 22 : until network lifetime close (e.g., all nodes dead or % threshold reached) 23 : Output performance metrics Terminate

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The election of CHs in LEACH is governed by a threshold function, expressed in Equation (8) (Tadros *et al.*, 2023):

$$T(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{p}{1 - p \times \left(r \times \text{mod} \left(\frac{1}{p} \right) \right)}, & \text{if } n \in G \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Where p is the desired percentage of CHs in the network, r denotes the current round, and G is the set of nodes that have not served as CHs in the last $(1/p)$ rounds. This threshold ensures that the CH role is rotated among nodes over successive rounds, thereby balancing the energy consumption across the network.

By employing this probabilistic CH selection mechanism in combination with localized data aggregation, LEACH effectively extends the network lifetime and enhances scalability.

3.3 Simulation Setup

The performance evaluation of LEACH was conducted in MATLAB R2021a on a system with Intel® Core™ i5 processor (2.4 GHz), 8 GB RAM, and Windows 10 (64-bit) operating system. The WSN was modelled as a ZigBee-based network for farm microclimate monitoring, with sensor nodes uniformly grid-spaced in a 100 x 100 m² field and a static Base Station (BS) located at the centre. Each node was initialized with equal energy and equipped with sensing and communication capabilities.

In this study, LEACH was implemented under different configurations of cluster head (CH)

percentage, node density, and packet size to determine the optimal network configuration, while performance was evaluated using both theoretical and empirical propagation models to compare protocol efficiency under idealized and realistic conditions. Each simulation scenario was executed for multiple rounds, and the results were averaged to minimize the effect of stochastic variations in CH selection. The simulations employed the empirical radio energy model described in sub-section 3.1 together with the LEACH operations detailed in sub-section 3.2. The Theoretical Energy Model (TEM) was derived from the conventional free-space and two-ray ground propagation assumptions, whereas the Empirical Energy Model (EEM) incorporated cassava-farm-specific attenuation parameters were obtained from prior measurements. Consistent with established WSN energy models, the energy consumption associated with sensing operations was considered negligible relative to transmission and reception, and thus excluded from the analysis (Amutha *et al.*, 2020).

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Key simulation parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters used for Network Simulation

Parameters	Value
Number of Sink	1
Number of Nodes	30, 60, 80, 100
Simulation Area	100 m × 100 m
Base Station Position	(50, 50)
Location of nodes	uniform grid distribution
Initial Energy	0.5 J/node
Number of Cluster Heads	5 - 20% of alive sensor nodes
E_{DA}	5 nJ/bit
$E_{amp}(n1)$	0.0021612 pJ/bit/m ^{2.55}
$E_{amp}(n2)$	0.000016285 pJ/bit/m ^{4.25}
V_s	3.3 V
I_{TX}	38.8 mA (Cluster Member), 44.7 mA (Cluster Head)
I_{RX}	29.7 mA
E_{elect} (Theoretical)	50 nJ/bit
E_{fs}	10 pJ/bit/m ²
E_{mp}	0.0013 pJ/bit/m ⁴
Size of Data Packets	200, 400, 600, 800, 1000 bits
Size of Control Packets	100 bits
Propagation model	Theoretical, Empirical

3.4 Performance Metric

The evaluation of the LEACH protocol in this study was based on two key performance metrics: Average Energy Consumption (AEC) and Network Lifetime (NL). AEC serves as a fundamental indicator of energy efficiency in

WSNs by quantifying the mean residual energy of sensor nodes at each simulation round, as defined in Equation (9), thereby reflecting the rate at which network resources are depleted under varying configurations (Ktari *et al.*, 2025).

$$AEC(r) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N E_i(r) \quad (9)$$

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Where N denotes the total number of sensor nodes and $E_i(r)$ represents the residual energy of the i^{th} node at round r . Lower values of AEC correspond to higher levels of energy dissipation, whereas higher values indicate improved energy preservation across the network.

In addition to AEC, NL was employed to capture the sustainability of the network over time. NL is defined as the total number of simulation rounds completed until the first node exhausts its energy, a widely used metric for benchmarking clustering protocols in energy-constrained WSNs (Amutha *et al.*, 2020). This measure provides direct insight into the ability of LEACH to balance energy consumption across nodes and extend the operational lifetime of the network under different configurations.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The simulation results for the LEACH protocol under different network configurations and propagation models are presented in Figures 4–7. The evaluation considered variations in CH percentage, node density, and packet size, with a maximum of 1000 simulation rounds applied for the comparative analysis of the two energy models namely; the Theoretical Energy Model (TEM) and the Empirical Energy Model (EEM).

4.1.1 Cluster Head Percentage

Figure 4 shows the average energy consumption when CH percentage varied from 5% to 20% of Alive Nodes (AN). Energy use rose progressively with higher CH ratios, though at different rates across configurations, indicating that certain CH levels yield more favourable energy performance. Figure 5 presents the corresponding network lifetime, where excessive CH percentages shortened lifetime due to overhead, while very low ratios reduced coverage.

Figure 4: Energy consumption for varying number of cluster heads

Figure 5: Network lifetime for varying number of cluster heads

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4.1.2 Node Density

Figure 6 illustrates energy consumption for node populations ranging from 30 to 100. Results show a consistent increase in consumption with higher density, reflecting greater communication overhead. Figure 7 shows that lifetime does not

scale proportionally; sparse networks (30 nodes) conserved energy but suffered from limited coverage and poor redundancy, whereas very dense deployments (100 nodes) depleted energy rapidly due to excessive communication.

Figure 6: Energy consumption for varying number of nodes

Figure 7: Network lifetime for varying number of nodes

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4.1.3 Packet Size

Figure 8 presents energy consumption for packet sizes ranging from 200 to 1000 bits. Larger packets increased energy use, while smaller packets reduced per-transmission cost but required more frequent communication. Figure 9 shows the corresponding effect on network

lifetime: large packets accelerated node depletion, whereas very small packets introduced overhead that reduced efficiency.

Figure 8: Energy consumption for varying packet sizes

Figure 9: Network lifetime for varying packet sizes

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4.1.4 Radio Energy Models

A comparative assessment between TEM and EEM is shown in Figure 7. This experiment was conducted for a maximum of 1000 rounds to capture long-term behaviour. The results reveal

distinct differences in average energy consumption between the two models, with the empirical model reflecting dissipation patterns that are more representative of the cassava farm propagation environment.

Figure 10: Energy consumption for empirical and theoretical energy model

4.2 Discussion

The results show that the number of CHs significantly affects energy consumption. Increasing the CH percentage from 5% to 20% led to higher energy dissipation due to additional aggregation and long-range transmissions. However, very low CH ratios reduced energy use at the cost of poor coverage and unbalanced clustering. Among the tested values, the 10% configuration achieved the best balance between energy efficiency and coverage, consistent with findings in the literature which emphasize optimal CH selection as a critical factor for minimizing energy wastage in LEACH-based networks (Qin *et al.*, 2012).

Node density also had a marked influence on energy consumption. Networks with 100 nodes depleted energy more rapidly due to increased communication overhead, while sparse deployments with 30 nodes suffered from limited redundancy and reduced coverage. The 60-node configuration performed best, striking a balance between energy efficiency, adequate coverage, and the requirements of microclimate monitoring systems. This outcome aligns with Dongre and Gulhane (2014), who observed that dense networks incur higher per-node communication costs, while excessively sparse networks compromise connectivity and fault tolerance.

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Packet size variation further demonstrated a direct correlation with energy use. Larger packets of 1000 bits accelerated energy depletion due to increased transmission cost, whereas smaller packets of 200 bits reduced energy consumption but introduced high control overhead from frequent transmissions. A packet size of 400 bits was found to be the most efficient configuration, achieving a balance between energy preservation and communication reliability required for effective microclimate monitoring. This observation supports earlier work by Razzaq *et al.* (2018), which highlighted the strong influence of packet size on overall WSN energy efficiency.

A comparison between the TEM and the EEM over 1000 simulation rounds further revealed significant differences. TEM, based on free-space and two-ray ground assumptions, showed a gradual, nearly linear increase in average energy consumption, reaching only 0.18 J by the 1000th round. In contrast, EEM exhibited a steep rise, reaching approximately 0.5 J by round 400, after which it saturated. This higher dissipation reflects vegetation-induced attenuation, multipath effects, and canopy moisture present in cassava farm environments. Similar observations were reported in Rhim *et al.* (2018), who showed that empirical models consistently predict higher energy costs than free-space or two-ray assumptions. These results underscore the importance of adopting empirical propagation models for agricultural WSNs, as theoretical models may lead to overly optimistic

estimates of energy performance and network lifetime. Overall, the optimum LEACH configuration was achieved with 10% CHs, 60 nodes, and 400-bit packets under empirical propagation conditions, which collectively minimized energy consumption while maintaining adequate coverage and extended network lifetime.

5. CONCLUSION

This study analysed the performance of the LEACH protocol in ZigBee-based Wireless Sensor Networks by integrating an empirical path loss model derived from cassava farm measurements and benchmarking it against conventional theoretical models. The empirical radio energy model was implemented in Matrix Laboratory (MATLAB)-based simulations to capture realistic propagation effects, with Average Energy Consumption and Network Lifetime adopted as the principal performance metrics. Results demonstrated that network configuration strongly influences energy dynamics, with a 10% cluster head ratio, 60-node deployment, and 400-bit packet size emerging as the optimal configuration for minimizing energy consumption while maintaining adequate coverage and reliable communication. Comparative analysis further showed that the Empirical Energy Model predicted substantially higher energy expenditure than the Theoretical Energy Model, underscoring the limitations of free-space and two-ray ground assumptions in vegetation-dense agricultural environments.

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Although LEACH exhibited satisfactory efficiency under optimized conditions, its probabilistic cluster-head selection disregards residual energy, leading to uneven depletion and reduced lifetime. Future work should focus on developing energy-aware and hybrid clustering protocols, supported by bio-inspired and swarm-intelligence optimization frameworks, to achieve more balanced energy utilization and extend the

sustainability of WSN deployments in precision agriculture.

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